

ISic1207

Epitaph for Nemeris, a goldsmith

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

cippus

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

From the area of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8706

Physical Description

A rectangular sandstone cippus, intact and finished on all sides, but uneven below; minor damage to the upper left of the front face

Dimensions

Height 40 cm

Width 31 cm

Depth 14.5 cm

Layout

Five lines of Greek letters, centred on the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Slightly crudely incised simple broad letters without serifs. Nu i sregular; epsilon has slightly shorter middle bar; mu has slightly inward leaning first and last strokes, the mid-strokes reach down to the base-line; rho has a small eye, not always fully closed; alpha has broken bar; omega varies between open circle closed by horizontal bar and closed ovoid form with horizontal bar; phi has a small circular eye; sigma has standard form with horizontal top and bottom strokes; omicron is approximately the same size as other letters.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 30-45 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not recorded mm

Text

1. Νεμέριε
2. Γρανῶνι
3. Νυμφόδωρε
4. χρυσοχόε
5. χάρε

Apparatus

Text after earlier editions and photograph
Salinas, Νεμέρις; Kaibel, Νεμέρις or Νεμέρι[ε]
Salinas, Νυμφόδωρι

Translation (en)

Nemerios Granonis Nymphodoros, goldsmith, farewell!

Commentary

The reading of line 1 is problematic; traces of a letter seem to be visible after the final iota, but whether a sigma or a faint epsilon very uncertain. Manni Piraino rejected the presence of a letter and argued for a vocative in -i from forms (common in Sicily) in -is; on the other hand, the vocative Νεμέριε from the well attested Greek rendering Νεμέριος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%9D%CE%B5%CE%BC%CE%AD%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BF%CF%82] is straightforward. A Numerius Granonius, N.f. Cat(ulus?), domo Luceria, who served in Roman legions of the mid-C1 BC is known from an Athenian inscription (CIL 1 (2).791 [<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/520528>]). Manni Piraino (in IGPalermo [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/F66S4X3M>]) dates this inscription to the C2 AD, apparently on the basis of the nomenclature and assumptions about the letter forms. The principal area of the necropolis, however, is archaeologically Hellenistic (and not later than the early C2 BC), and only a single inscription from the general area of Tripi (the Latin fragment, ISic 0623 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0623>]) is certainly from the imperial period. There is nothing about the letter forms themselves which requires an imperial date (closed omega with variable forms is common in the later Hellenistic, and the absence of any lunate forms is notable), so the argument appears to rest on historical assumptions regarding the Italic/Roman elements in the name, which do not follow proper Roman conventions regarding e.g. filiation, and employ Sicilian Greek orthography. In other words, an earlier, rather than a later date seems more plausible, of the second century BC?

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae

Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0382b (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika 6*. Palermo. At 126

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 464 no.a

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezzenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5208b

Manni Piraino, M. T. 1976. Contribution Épigraphique à l'Étude de l'esclavage en Sicile. *Actes du Colloque 1973 sur l'Esclavage*. Besançon. pp. 385-397. At 392

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 20 n.73

Sofia, G. 2015. Abakainon. Nella dimora di Ade. La necropoli in contrada Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME). At 108 fig.113

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Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas